

LiftWEC

DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW CLASS OF WAVE ENERGY CONVERTER
BASED ON HYDRODYNAMIC LIFT FORCES

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Report on physical modelling of 3D LiftWEC concepts

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

After a successful experimental test campaign of the LiftWEC two-dimension model in Ecole Centrale de Nantes (ECN) in June and July 2021, a three-dimensional model of the LiftWEC concept was tested in September and October 2022. The 3D model was designed, built, assembled and commissioned by ECN. It has 1.49m foil length and allows testing of configurations with one or two foils, with adjustments before each test of the foil angle of attack. The model was tested in the ECN Hydrodynamics and Ocean Engineering Tank (HOET) and was fixed under a six-degree motion hexapod (or Stewart platform) at the centre of the basin, allowing controlled motion of the model substructure. The idea behind this approach is to test the concept in fixed conditions and in dynamic motion to characterise the influence of a floating device. This allowed fixed model testing at different rotor depth and wave direction. The angular motion of the rotor was controlled using a power take-off (PTO) system consisting of an electrical machine which can be operated in fixed position, speed or torque control. The quantities measured are the PTO torque, absolute angular position of the rotor, radial and tangential loads on the axis of each foil and wave elevation upstream and downstream of the model. From those measured quantities, rotor velocity and acceleration as well as captured power can be inferred.

The present document describes in detail the test campaign carried out in September and October 2022 with the 3D LiftWEC model. It gives details on the model setup, testing carried out, data processing and validation. The data and the full test matrix were published in Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669668> and are now free to access.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the experimental testing of the LiftWEC 3D model in the wave and towing tank at Ecole Centrale de Nantes (ECN) in September and October 2022. This document provides detailed information on the experimental setup, wave testing carried out and the data acquisition and validation.

The open access dataset is available from the online repository Zenodo, with DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669668>.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 WAVE BASIN

The Hydrodynamics and Ocean Engineering Tank at Centrale Nantes offers a 30-meter wide, 50-meter long, 5-meter deep testing volume. The wavemaker control system was upgraded in May 2022 with new electrical actuators, servo-controllers, other electrical and mechanical parts, and the new version of the wave generation software.

Figure 2-1: Hydrodynamics and Ocean Engineering Tank (HOET)

The tank is equipped with a segmented wave maker, visible in Figure 2-1, composed of 48 hinged flaps distributed over the width of the basin. The wave maker control software, used together with enhanced control laws from the literature and implemented at LHEEA (Dalrymple method, Molin method (disc or rectangle)), can generate either idealised theoretical waves (e.g. monochromatic waves, wave packets) or complex representative sea states. This powerful wave maker can generate waves larger than a meter in wave height at specific periods, as shown by its operational diagram shown in Figure 2-2. At the other end of the basin, a seven meters long passive stainless steel beach with quadratic profile dissipates most of the wave energy through breaking processes.

The tank is also equipped with several gantries, to allow staff access to models and support instrumentation, signal conditioning and acquisition materials.

Figure 2-2: Performances of ECN's HOET wave maker

Water in the tank is fresh water that remains permanently. The gravitational acceleration g is equal to 9.80824 at Nantes (value from <https://www.sensorsone.com/local-gravity-calculator>).

Figure 2-3 shows the amplitude reflection rates in the wave basin. In most wave cases generated during this project, the wave period is below 3 seconds, corresponding to a wavelength of about 14m. In this period range, the reflection at the beach is between 5 and 10%.

Figure 2-3 : Reflection rates in the wave basin

2.2 MODEL DESIGN AND SETUP

LiftWEC deliverable LW-D04-05 gives details of the model in the design phase and deliverable LW-D04-06 give pictures and details of the built model. This section includes the main model parameters that are required to describe the hydrodynamic characteristics and the data acquired. A picture of the model outside the tank is shown in Figure 2-4 and the model in the tank is shown in Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-4: Overview of the 3D LiftWEC model outside the tank

Figure 2-5: Overview of the 3D LiftWEC model in the tank, under the hexapod

Figure 2-6: Overview of the 3D LiftWEC model in the tank, under the hexapod

The experimental setup is composed of the following elements:

- The tripod connected to the tank floor at 5m depth and creating a rigid platform about 2m above the water surface. It is placed at the centre of the tank so that the model is 17.15m from the wavemaker. Its dry part is visible in Figure 2-5.
- A six-degree motion hexapod that was available in ECN and capable of holding the model at a given fixed position during a test, or to create a controlled motion. It is placed upside down on the tripod platform, with its motion controlled side placed near the water surface so that the model can be held at desired locations between 0.3 and 0.6m above the water surface.
- Two bridges supporting the wave gauges in front and behind the model
- The 3D LiftWEC model, built for this test campaign and shown in Figure 2-4. It is fixed under the hexapod moving plate and described in more details below.

The 3D LiftWEC model is composed of a rigid structure made of steel and aluminium. The top part of the structure is placed between 0.3 and 0.6m above the water surface to avoid interaction with the waves and is held from above with the hexapod. Two vertical truss on either side of the model connect the top structure (above the water surface) to the model shaft between 0.5 and 0.8m under the water surface. It has a minimal tube sections to reduce its interaction with waves. The model rotor is composed of the hydrofoils, a central shaft and holding arms connecting the foils to the shaft. The shaft is held between the vertical trusses with bearings, it is connected to the electrical PTO on one side, and, on the other side, to a magnetic encoder and slip ring to transfer load cells signals. Table 2-1 gives the main geometry of the model and wave tank.

The foil pitch is defined as zero when the foil cord is parallel to the direction of motion. It is positive when the leading edge is further away from the rotor axis of rotation. This is illustrated in Figure 2-10.

Figure 2-7 shows a close-up of model rotor visible from the above water video camera. Figure 2-8 shows a view of the model from the underwater video camera.

Description	Unit	Dimension
Tank length	m	50
Tank width	m	30
Tank depth	m	5
Model distance to wavemaker	m	17.15
Hydrofoil length	m	1.49
Hydrofoil profile		NACA0015, curved with 0.3m radii
Hydrofoil chord length	m	0.3
Hydrofoil chord curve radius	m	0.3
Hydrofoil truncated trailing edge thickness	Mm	2
Rotor diameter	m	0.6
Pitch angles	degrees	[-12, -8, -4, 0, 4, 8, 12]
Depth of rotor axis	m	Adjustable between 0.5 and 0.8
Number of hydrofoils		1 or 2
Winglets dimensions	mm	30mm outside foil section

Table 2-1: ECN 3D experimental setup main geometry

Figure 2-7: Closer view of the model rotor from above water surface

Figure 2-8: Overview of the model from underwater

2.3 INSTRUMENTATION

2.3.1 Wave gauges

Ten wave gauges, measuring water surface elevation, were deployed in the tank for wave calibration, with the model installed at its test location without hydrofoils. The list of wave gauges and locations are in Table 2-2 and illustrated in Figure 2-9. This setup allows measurement of the reflected waves in front and behind the model with four wave gauges aligned at the centre of the basin either side of the model. In addition, one wave gauge placed beside the model, in the direction perpendicular to the wave propagation direction, gives a wave measurement at the same distance from the paddles.

During testing with the active part of the model (rotor, foils, etc.), wave gauge 5 was removed to leave space for the rotation of the foils.

Wave gauge ID	Wave gauge length (m)	Position X (m) (distance to paddles)	Position Y (m) (Relative to basin centreline)	Comments
1	0.6	14.95	0	
2	0.6	15.10	0	
3	0.6	15.45	0	
4	0.6	16.15	0	
5	0.6	17.15	0	Wave calibration only
6	0.6	18.15	0	
7	0.6	18.3	0	
8	0.6	18.65	0	
9	0.6	19.35	0	
10	0.6	17.15	3	

Table 2-2: Position of wave gauges in the basin (model scale)

Figure 2-9 : Illustration of wave gauges position in the basin.

All wave gauges were calibrated before installation in the basin, with the same cables and acquisition system as used during tank testing. The calibration rig is outside the basin and composed of a controlled linear actuator and a tank filled with water pumped from the basin to ensure same water conductivity. Calibration results for all wave gauges are in appendix C.

2.3.2 Load cells

Eight load cells measured the load applied from the two foils on the rotor arms. Two are located on either side of each foil and measure the load in radial and tangential directions. The list of load cells and their measured parameter is in Table 2-3.

Sensor	Direction	Side	Foil
F1	Radial	Motor	1
F2	Tangential	Motor	1
F3	Radial	Motor	2
F4	Tangential	Motor	2
F5	Radial	Collector	1
F6	Tangential	Collector	1
F7	Radial	Collector	2
F8	Tangential	Collector	2

Table 2-3: List of load cells and measured parameter

The description of measured radial and tangential forces is shown in Figure 2-10. The loads are measured at a distance of a quarter of the foil cord length from the leading edge and the direction of the radial force is parallel to a line passing through the axis of rotation and the centre of the foil (half foil cord). The radial force is positive when the force applied by the foil on the rotor is directed away from the centre of rotation. The tangential force is positive when the force applied by the foil on the rotor is directed towards the leading edge, in this direction the foil is accelerating the rotor or generating power.

Figure 2-10: Illustration of radial and tangential force measured by the load cells

The load cells selected are manufactured by the German company HBK, see picture in Figure 2-11. The models details are:

- K-Z6-F-C3-0050-N-S3-N (+/-500N capacity) for the radial direction
- K-Z6-F-C3-0030-N-S3-N (+/-300N capacity) for the tangential direction

Figure 2-11: Picture of a load cells use during the experiments

All load cells were checked before installation on the model and were calibrated once on the model with final cabling structure, through the arms and slip ring. The calibration results are in appendix D

2.3.3 PTO torque transducer

A torque transducer with a torque rating of 100Nm, measures the torque on the motor shaft. It is produced by the German company ETH-messtechnik and the model is DRBK II 100 A. The sensor is located in the motor dry enclosure and in series between the motor shaft and the main rotor shaft holding arms and foils.

The torque transducer could not be calibrated at ECN and the measurements are based on the sensor datasheet and the factory certificate in Appendix E.

Figure 2-12: Picture of the torque transducer used during the experiments

2.3.4 Angular position

A magnetic encoder measures the rotor angular position, it is placed in the dry enclosure on the slip ring side of the model. The moving part is attached to the shaft in line with the motor and torque meter and it has a resolution of 4096 pulses per turn, corresponding to an angular resolution of 0.09 degree. The encoder is produced by the German company Automation Sensorik Messtechnik (ASM). The magnetic disk model is PMIR5-50-64-M-83-AB and that of the reader head is PMIS4-50-64-20KHZ-TTL-Z3-3M-S

The encoder has a reference position, which is used to calibrate the absolute position measurement. When the encoder is turned on, the absolute position is not known but when the reference position is sensed (after one turn maximum) the acquisition system corrects the measured value to the known position of the reference. This action was done before testing, each time the acquisition system was restarted, and therefore does not affect the acquired files, which always give the absolute position.

The angle value is zero when the line passing through the centre of the rotor and the centre of the foil (half of the cord length) is vertical and the foil 1 is at its highest position. The recorded value is wrapped between 0 and 360 degrees.

2.3.5 Hexapod motion

The hexapod operates with its own software, independent to all other control and acquisition equipment in the basin. Its motion measurement, derived from the six electrical motors positions, cannot be logged and synchronised with other measurements. Therefore, the model motion, when the hexapod is running, was measured using Qualisys motion cameras. This approach also has the advantage that there is no risk of a wrong transfer function between motor positions and actual model six-degree position.

The Qualisys camera system was composed of three cameras placed under the tripod, each one under one leg of the tripod. Four markers were placed on top of the hexapod moving plate at locations visible from all the three cameras. See Figure 2-13. This allowed the generation of a rigid body to measure all six-degree motions of the model.

Figure 2-13: Moving plate of the hexapod, above the model, with Qualisys reflective markers

2.4 VIDEO CAMERAS

Two PTZ CCTV camera, with HD resolution and an optical zoom of x25, recorded video in all model tests, these were starting with the wavemaker trigger. An underwater video camera was placed at the bottom of the tank (on the incoming wave side). The camera and its waterproof housing are shown in Figure 2-14. The second camera was placed above water surface.

Figure 2-14: Underwater video camera used in the experiments

2.5 POWER TAKE-OFF AND CONTROL SYSTEM

The model power take-off is a brushless permanent magnet electrical machine, connected to the rotor main shaft through a torque meter. It is composed of:

- Motor Kollmorgen Catridge C061B-13-3105 with the following specifications:
 - High Resolution Sine-Cosine-resolver, Singleturn, Heidenhain ECN, EnDat
 - Stall Torque = 32.60Nm Peak Torque = 75.6 Nm
 - Voltage Supply = 230 VAC Rated Speed = 1950 rpm
- Drive AKD-P02406-NBCC-x069
- Dump load regen external resistor BAF(U) 200-33 (200W)

The motor control system allows the following control modes:

- “Fixed position” mode: the rotor can be placed and held in position at any angle.
- “Constant speed” mode: from its starting position, in “fixed position” mode, the motor accelerates up to the required speed. The acceleration starts at a time (delay after the wave generation starts) that must be set before the wave starts. It will be used to control the phase angle between the wave and the rotor position. Once the rotor reaches the required speed, the controller modulates the rotor torque to follow that target speed. This is illustrated in Figure 2-15 where t_0 is the time when the wavemaker starts and t_1 is the chosen delay when the rotor speed control starts. This speed control mode can also be used in the absence of incoming waves. In this configuration, the PTO drives the rotor at a constant speed. This approach can be used to investigate the wave radiation characteristics of the device.
- “torque control” mode: at negative or zero speed, the rotor torque is set to zero. For positive rotational speeds, a damping torque (proportional to the rotational speed) is applied to the rotor, resisting its motion. The value of the torque applied is capped i.e. as the rotor speed increases, there is a point where the torque applied by the PTO is no longer proportional to the rotational speed but becomes constant. If the rotational speed goes down, in such a way that the damping torque falls below the torque cap, then the torque becomes again proportional to the rotational velocity. This control strategy is illustrated in Figure 2-16. The damping coefficient and the torque limit can be set (within the limits of the motor capabilities). The system might not be self-starting with this control configuration, in which case, the torque control sequence will be preceded by a short speed control sequence to get the rotor spinning.
- “Speed time series” mode: this mode generates a controlled motion with any speed profile programmed in a text file, giving the speed at each time step of one millisecond. It is designed to follow the speed time series in the file and repeat the same cycle until the test stops, therefore the speed at the beginning and at the end of the file must be the same.

Figure 2-15: Constant speed mode

Figure 2-16: Torque mode

The control of the PTO will be implemented using a National Instruments CompactRIO connected to the motor drive. The control algorithms will be programmed in LabVIEW.

2.6 DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM

The control and acquisition system, illustrated in Figure 2-17, is composed of:

- A CompactRio, CRio 9045, for motor control and for measurement of rotor torque and position. It records at 500Hz.
- Two HBM Quantum MX1601B signal-conditioning unit recording all wave gauges and load cells. It records at 500Hz.
- The Qualisys Track Manager (QTM) software to analyse the data from motion cameras, calculate and record the motion time series of the model. It records at 200Hz.

All acquisition systems are independent but a Labview program, named CN-master, communicates with QTM and Catman (software controlling the two HBM Quantum), it can start the two systems and give their file names. It also controls a trigger that starts acquisition on the CompactRio and the video recording.

Figure 2-17: Illustration of the motor control and data acquisition system

3 EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

3.1 TEST METHODOLOGY

During this test campaign more than 500 tests were carried out. The specific wave conditions and model configuration was set for each test as per the test requirements and was logged in the test matrix, see appendix A.

The wave calibration sequence, applied to each test, follows the steps below:

- Setup of the data acquisition system for the next test.
- Selection of the next wave case, following the test requirements.
- Start data acquisition from CN-master when waves in the basin are visually settled and the wave heights measured on the wave gauges are below about 2% of the height or significant wave height of the next wave case.
- Wait about 10 seconds to record still water conditions and check the data recording started with the trigger and all sensors show reasonable values.
- Start the wavemaker. This sets a trigger to ON, and this trigger is recorded on a channel on the wave gauge data acquisition systems so that the wave calibration data can be synchronised with data during model testing.
- The test duration is set and the wavemaker stops automatically

- Stop the acquisition system manually after the wave generation system has stopped.
- Verify the raw data file is saved correctly in the acquisition computer

Note: in wave calibration tests, only the Quantums were used for data acquisition, therefore all channels from CompactRIO and QTM are not available in data files.

The model testing method, applied to each test, follows the steps below:

- Setup of the data acquisition system for the next test.
- Setup of the motor control and acquisition system for the next test.
 - When the foil to wave phase angle needs to be set, the position control mode is used to place the foil at the required initial position and the control is then switched to the desired control mode with a calculated time delay from the wavemaker trigger to start the rotation.
- Select the next wave case, following the test requirements.
- Start all the recording with the Labview Master program (QTM, Quantums and Crio) when waves in the basin are visually settled and the wave heights measured on the wave gauges are below about 2% of the height or significant wave height of the next wave case.
- Wait about 10 seconds to record still water conditions and check the data recording started with the trigger and all sensors show reasonable values.
- Start the wavemaker. This sets a trigger to ON, and this trigger is recorded on a channel on all three data acquisition systems so that all data can be synchronised with trigger rising edge. The trigger also starts the two video recording.
- Check the data recording started with the trigger and all sensors show reasonable values.
- The wavemaker runs for a set duration and when it stops, its trigger is set to OFF
- Manually stop all data acquisition systems about 15 seconds after the wavemaker stops.
- After the test stops, verify the data files and video file are saved correctly in the acquisition computers

Each test has a unique test number recorded in the test matrix together with relevant test conditions and comments. There are gaps in the test numbers on the test matrix; they correspond to discarded data.

3.2 MODEL MOTION PROFILES

The model motion profiles describe the motion of the entire structure of the model controlled by the motion of the hexapod. Most of the motion profiles are defined in the test matrix (fixed position or constant speed). However, in some tests, the motion profile was more complex and additional details are provided in this section.

3.2.1 Model circular motion profile

The model circular motion is indicated in the test matrix with “Motion profile” entry such as “T2p0_A0p075”. This means a circular rotation of the model around its initial position in the same

direction as water particles orbital motions in waves. In this example, the rotation period is 2 seconds and the amplitude is 0.075m.

The test matrix input “Model motion phase” gives the phase between the wave crest and the model passing its highest position. A negative values means the mode reaches its highest position after the

3.2.2 Compliance test

In only two tests called compliance tests, the model motion generated by the hexapod consisted in a motion profile with two sinusoidal oscillation combined, see an example in Figure 3-1. In this figure, the foil motion profile is the predicted foil motion combining hexapod motion and model rotor motion. In the test matrix the entry “Model motion profile” is “Struct-4”. This corresponds to a main oscillation with 2 seconds period and 30mm amplitude, this main motion is multiplied by a 1 second period sinusoidal function. The expected motion variations were too large for the hexapod and it is best to use the measured model motion to analyse this test data.

Figure 3-1: Example of compliance test motion profile

3.2.3 Rotor linear acceleration

In some tests, the rotor speed was ramping up at constant acceleration rate until a plateau at constant speed and then decelerating at the same rate as the constant acceleration rate. These tests are marked in the test matrix entry “Rotor motion profile” with names “LinAcc” 1 to 3. The corresponding motion profiles are listed in Table 3-1.

Rotor motion profile	LinAcc - 1	LinAcc - 2	LinAcc - 3
Acceleration rate (rad/s ²)	0.257	1.019	0.064
Rotor speed at plateau (rad/s)	4	8	2
Plateau duration (s)	7.8	3.9	15.6
Deceleration rate (rad/s ²)	-0.257	-1.019	-0.064

Table 3-1: Velocity parameters of the rotor in the linear acceleration tests

3.2.4 Rotor motion time series

In some tests, a motion time series was used to vary the rotor speed within a wave period and repeat itself each wave period. The variable speed cases are named “Control 2” and “Control 4” in the test matrix entry “Rotor motion profile”. The full rotor motion time series can be read in the data files of the corresponding tests.

3.3 TEST MATRIX

The test matrix in this section provides the final information on the list of tests carried out during the test campaign. It includes the wave characteristics, model configuration and PTO control strategy. The test matrix is presented in appendix A and gives all parameters required for data analysis. Represented columns are:

- **Test num:** The unique test number, which is used in all the project reports, data files, etc.
- **Wave type:** type of wave generated during the test, it may be:
 - IN AIR: model test outside the tank
 - Calib: if the wave type contains this word, the test is a wave calibration test
 - ZERO: model in water but no wave generated
 - RW = Regular waves
 - PW = Polychromatic waves, containing five regular wave components. Their definition is in Appendix B
 - IW = Irregular waves (Jonswap spectrum)
- **WaveCalibTestNum:** test number in which the same wave characteristics were calibrated
- **IW_Seed:** Irregular wave seed, corresponding to a given random phase modifier to convert the wave spectrum to a wave time series. Each seed number correspond to a given wave time series.
- **T/Tp(s):** wave period (regular) or Peak period (irregular)
- **H/Hs(m):** wave height (regular) or Significant wave height (irregular)

- **Foil1 phase:** Requested phase angle between wave peak and foil 1 position at quarter cord. In fixed rotor position tests, this gives the fixed position of the rotor for all the test duration.
- **RotorPeriod:** Duration in seconds for one full rotation of the rotor
- **Vrotor_Rad_sec:** Rotor speed in constant speed mode
- **Rotor motion profile:** rotational velocity profile of the rotor. This can be:
 - **Constant:** the rotor speed is constant during all test after reaching its set speed
 - **Fixed:** the rotor shaft did not move during the test
 - **LinAcc 1 or 2 or 3:** This is an acceleration controlled mode in which the rotor accelerates slowly, stays at a set speed for some time and then decelerates slowly. Three motion profiles were tested and are described in section 0
 - **Control 2 or 4:** this is a variable speed test with a motion time series repeated each wave period. The time series is described in section 3.2.4.
- **Foils on model:** Number of foils on mode
- **Rot axis initial depth:** Depth of the rotor axis at the start of each test. This remained fixed except when “model motion profile” is not “zero”.
- **Initial Orientation [°]:** Angle between the model and the wave direction (yaw). Zero degree means the rotor axis of rotation is perpendicular to the wave direction
- **Model motion profile:** Profile of the motion set by the hexapod. This is explained in more details in section 3.2.1 and 3.2.2.
- **Model motion phase:** phase of the model motion. This is explained in more details in section 3.2.1 and 3.2.2.
- **End plates:** True when end plates are placed at the end of the foil(s)
- **Pitch1:** Foil 1 angle value, “False” means this foil is not on the model
- **Pitch2:** Foil 2 angle value, “False” means this foil is not on the model
- **Comments:** Any comment or observation during the test

4 DATA PROCESSING

4.1 MERGED DATA FILE GENERATION

After testing, a Matlab code developed by ECN was used to merge the three data files into a single file including all the calibrated parameters sampled at 128 Hz and in SI units. The data processing done to merge all data files is:

- Open the three raw data files generated by the two acquisition systems, the CRio and Quantum.
- Select channels that need to be save for data analysis
- Find the rising edge of the wavemaker trigger signal in all data files and change the time reference to zero value at the corresponding line in the time series. The rising edge also corresponds to the start of wave generation.
- Resample the time series at the desired acquisition rate of 128Hz for this project.
- Save all selected channels in a single file.

It then generated for each test a Matlab and a text file. The name of the merged file is “LIFTWEC3D_XXX”, with XXX the test number described in the test matrix (see appendix A). It contains a Matlab structure with the following elements (the text file contains the same elements in the headers, except “II” and “Type”, followed by the numerical data):

- “date”: test date in Matlab number format
- “data”: test data with one column per parameter
- “Time”: time column corresponding to the “data” table. In this column, zero value corresponds to the first time step in which the wavemaker trigger value is high, which means the wavemaker is starting.
- “chanNames”: name of the header for each column in the “data” table.
- “chanUnits”: SI units corresponding to each column in the “data” table.
- “testnum”: Test number corresponding to the list of tests in the test matrix section 3.3
- “family”: All sensors are sorted in families to simplify the analysis with the ECN Matlab code. This may not be required for further analysis
- “II”: This element is used in the ECN Matlab code to find a column in the “data” element corresponding to a given sensor. This may not be required for further analysis
- “type”: This element is used in the ECN Matlab code to choose the type of analysis to be done for each test. This may not be required for further analysis

During wave calibration, the list of channels in the data elements and listed in “chanNames” are:

- 2 columns with water temperature and conductivity.
- 1 columns with wavemaker trigger in Volts. This column is not needed for further analysis, it was used to synchronise the data files.
- “WGx”: 10 columns with Wave gauges (WG) 1 to 10 measurement in meter. “x” is the wave gauge number.

During model testing, the list of channels in the data elements and listed in “chanNames” are:

- 2 columns with water temperature and conductivity.
- 2 columns with wavemaker trigger in binary format and in Volts. These columns are not needed for further analysis, they were used to synchronise the data files.
- “WGx”: 10 columns with Wave gauges (WG) measurements in meter (WG5 was removed and the WG5 data should not be used). X is the wave gauge number.
- “Fx”: 8 columns with force measurement (F) in Newton from the 8 load cells on the model. “x” is the load cell number.
- “Speed”: The rotor speed in radian per second
- “Motortorque_Cor”: The motor estimated torque in Newton meter.
- “Torquemeter_Cor”: The torque measured at the torque meter in Newton meter.
- “Cpt_position_aux”: The rotor position in degree.

Details on the instrumentation and acquisition system are in section 2.3 and 2.4.

4.2 CALCULATION OF HYDRODYNAMIC LOADS AND TORQUE

Due to physical constraints regarding placement of the load cells and the torque-meter, the measured quantities are not only representing the hydrodynamic load components on the foils. Other main components are:

- Hydrostatic loads on the foils (and the arms for the torque-meter)
- Centrifugal forces on the load cells.
- Rotor friction on the torque-meter.

This section describes methods to estimate and remove those unnecessary components from the sensors measurements, so that the corrected load in the data file corresponds as close as possible to the hydrodynamic forces applied on the foils.

4.2.1 Hydrostatic loads compensation

The load and torque sensors measure the static loads due to the weight of rotor parts they are connected to, and its influence on each load cell varies with the rotor position. Therefore, it is not possible to apply a simple offset for the whole duration of a test, the sensor offset is calculated and removed from the measurement times series in post processing. This was done in two phases:

- Calculation of the static load and torque curve versus rotor angular position for tests with a slow and constant velocity of 0.1 rad/sec. This test was done for all configurations, in water or in the dry tests. The data is analysed for each sensor and for multiple rotations and sorted based on the angular position between 0 and 360 degrees. The zero curve is then calculated using the Matlab default linear interpolation function “interp1” on the sorted sensor measurement versus angular position. The interpolated curve gives a value each 0.2 degree, from 0 to 360 degrees. A static load curve is shown as an example in Figure 4-1.
- Removing the static load and torque values from measurements for each relevant columns in each data file.

Figure 4-1: Example of zero reference curve measure in test 48 on load cell 1

4.2.2 Centrifugal force compensation

The rotation of the rotor results in a centrifugal force on the load cells. It is defined in Equation 1 with the mass in rotation “m” in kilogrammes connected to the load cell, the rotor rotational speed “ ω ” in rad/sec and the radius “R” between the centre of rotation and the centre of gravity of the mass “m” in metres. “ α ” is the angle between the direction of the force and the direction of measurement of the load cell. The rotation speed time series is measured for each test and the radius is 0.3m.

$$\text{Equation 1: } F_{cent} = m * \omega^2 * R * \cos(\alpha)$$

The mass connected to the sensors depends on whether radial or tangential measurements are considered. The load cells measuring radial forces are holding the foil but also the other load cells, measuring the tangential forces. The centre of gravity also changes with the foil pitch. Therefore, the value of the rotating mass and the position of its centre of gravity are not known accurately. It is however unlikely that the direction of the centrifugal force, which goes from the centre of rotation to the centre of gravity, is exactly aligned with the sensor radial direction. The centrifugal force therefore has not only components in the direction of the radial sensor but also in the direction of the tangential sensor and the value of α in Equation 1 is not accurately known.

Therefore, the mass component for each load cell and each pitch value was calculated from experimental results of tests 76 to 121, with constant speed rotation outside water. After zeroing the channels, as described in section 4.2, the force applied to the load cells is only the centrifugal force. The average force on the load cells for each test is given in Appendix F for tests without winglets and Appendix G for tests with winglets. The results with the two higher rotational speeds were used to calculate the average mass component for each load cell shown in Table 4-1. These masses were then used to calculate and remove the centrifugal force applied on each sensor using Equation 1 with $\alpha=0$.

no winglets								
Pitch	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
4	5.32	0.50	5.51	0.54	5.56	0.57	5.52	0.51
0	5.38	0.51	5.66	0.54	5.59	0.57	5.44	0.55
-4	5.46	0.53	0.00	0.00	5.73	0.57	0.00	0.00
-8	5.43	0.57	0.00	0.00	5.71	0.55	0.00	0.00
-12	5.53	0.56	0.00	0.00	5.74	0.58	0.00	0.00
with winglets								
Pitch	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
4	5.73	0.57	5.95	0.51	5.97	0.60	5.77	0.58
0	5.77	0.46	5.98	0.47	6.01	0.68	5.86	0.65
-4	5.82	0.60	0.00	0.00	6.07	0.59	0.00	0.00
-8	5.79	0.73	0.00	0.00	6.16	0.53	0.00	0.00
-12	5.93	0.61	0.00	0.00	6.19	0.61	0.00	0.00

Table 4-1: Estimated mass component for each load cell depending on foil pitch and the presence of winglets

4.2.3 Friction compensation on torque

The torque-meter is in the dry enclosure between the electrical motor and the rotor shaft. Hence, the measurements at constant speed include the torque due to hydrodynamic forces on the foil but also some mechanical friction on the seal and hydrodynamic friction on the arms, which are not used in the comparison with numerical modelling. The difference between torque measurement and torque induced by the hydrofoil was estimated from tests without foil on the rotor. During these tests, the measured torque is considered to be the friction torque only and equal to the friction force in tests with foils.

This assumption seems correct when comparing results in Table 4-2, for tests with and without foils. The torque meter measured non negligible torques without foils and at high speed. Taking this “0 foil” torque off from the torque measured with one or two foils, the measured torque per foil is similar.

Speed (rad/sec.)	Torquemeter (Nm)			Foil torque (Nm)		
	0 foil	1 foil	2 foil	1 foil	2 foil	2 foil /2
7.85	6.26	13.48	21.09	7.23	14.83	7.42
3.93	1.72	3.61	5.58	1.89	3.85	1.93
3.49	1.40	2.90	4.46	1.50	3.06	1.53
3.14	1.15	2.37	3.67	1.23	2.52	1.26
2.85	0.96	1.98	3.07	1.02	2.11	1.06
2.62	0.81	1.70	2.56	0.89	1.76	0.88
1.96	0.45	0.97	1.49	0.51	1.03	0.52
0.10	-0.01	-0.01	-0.03	0.00	-0.02	-0.01

Table 4-2: Average torque measured at constant speed, still water and with no foil, one or two foils on the rotor

This corrected torque measurement was also added to the data file so that it can be used for further analysis.

4.3 MERGED AND PROCESSED DATA FILES

In addition to the data collected in the merged files, described in section 4.1, the processed data with corrected loads and torques was added in new columns after the merged data. These new columns are calculated from the raw measurement, the load and torque zeroing described in section 4.2.1, the deduction of the centrifugal force on the load cells described in section 4.2.2 and the friction compensation on the torque value described in section 4.2.3.

The list of additional channels in the “data” elements and listed in “chanNames” are:

- “Fx_Cor”: 8 columns with force measurement, adjusted by removing the zero values and the centrifugal force. “x” is the load cell number
- “Motortorque_Cor”: The motor estimated torque in Newton meter adjusted by removing the zero values.
- “Torquemeter_Cor”: The torque measured in Newton meter at the torque meter adjusted by removing the zero values
- “TorqueAtFoil_Cor”: The corrected torque (Torquemeter_Cor) with, in addition, the friction compensation.

Details on the instrumentation and acquisition system are in section 2.3 and 2.4.

The name of the merged file for each test is “LIFTWEC3D_XXX_CorSC.mat”, with XXX the test number described in the test matrix.

These processed files were published in Zenodo under DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669668> and are now free to access.

5 APPENDICES

A. TEST MATRIX

Test num	Wave type	W_Calib_TestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
Inertia testing in air																		
72	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
73	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
74	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
75	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
76	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
77	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
78	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
79	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
80	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
81	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
92	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
93	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
94	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
95	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
96	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
82	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
83	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
84	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
85	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
86	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
87	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
88	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
89	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
90	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
91	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
102	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
103	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
104	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
105	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
106	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils

Test num	Wave type	W CalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
107	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
108	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
109	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
110	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
111	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
97	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
98	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
99	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
100	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
101	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
112	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
113	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
114	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
115	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
116	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
117	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
118	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
119	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
120	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
121	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
92	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
93	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
94	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
95	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
96	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
72	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
73	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
74	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
75	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
76	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
97	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
98	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
99	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
100	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
101	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
102	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
103	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
104	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
105	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
106	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
PLACE MODEL IN WATER WITHOUT FOILS																		
Wave Calibration																		
132	RW			1.4008	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
133	RW			1.6000	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
134	RW			1.8028	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
135	RW			2.0000	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
136	RW			2.2022	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
137	RW			2.4038	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
138	RW			2.0000	0.10				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
151	PW			2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
152	PW			2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
154	IW		Seed2	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Seeds 1 and 3 gave low quality spectrum (test discarded)
155	IW		Seed4	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
156	IW		Seed5	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
157	IW		Seed6	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	low quality spectrum (test discarded)
158	IW		Seed7	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
147	IW		Seed1	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
148	IW		Seed2	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	low quality spectrum (test discarded)
149	IW		Seed3	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
150	IW		Seed4	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
153	IW		Seed5	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
ADD FOIL1, SWITCH TO -4DEG PITCH																		
159	ZERO			-			62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
218	ZERO			-			62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
162	ZERO			-			0.799998129	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
163	ZERO			-			1.400933179	4.485	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
164	ZERO			-			1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
165	ZERO			-			1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
167	ZERO			-			1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
168	ZERO			-			2.202308204	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
169	ZERO			-			2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
177	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
254	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
176	ZERO				-		1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
171	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
172	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
173	ZERO				-		2.202308204	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
175	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
192	ZERO				-		1.802922613	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	these had to be changed to match the regular waves exact period
193	ZERO				-		2.403666912	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
178	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
179	ZERO				-		1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
180	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
181	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
182	ZERO				-		2.202308204	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
185	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
214	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
215	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
216	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
Reg Waves																		
187	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
188	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
194	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
190	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
191	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
195	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
196	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
197	RW	135		2.00	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
198	RW	135		2.00	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
199	RW	135		2.00	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
253	RW	72		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
256	RW	76		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
200	RW	133		1.60	0.15	90	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
201	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
202	RW	137		2.404	0.15	90	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
252	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat

Test num	Wave type	WCalbTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	FoilI phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
SUBSTRUCTURE MOTION TEST																		
224	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p118	0	False	-4	False	
226	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p118	-45	False	-4	False	
230	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p118	-90	False	-4	False	
237	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	
238	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-45	False	-4	False	
247	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-90	False	-4	False	
248	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-180	False	-4	False	
233	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	0	False	-4	False	
234	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-45	False	-4	False	
235	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-90	False	-4	False	
236	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-180	False	-4	False	
249	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T1p98_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	Rotor speed is 2rad/sec instead of 1.98
250	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T1p98_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	Rotor speed is 2rad/sec instead of 1.98
251	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T1p98_A0p075	0	False	-4	False	Rotor speed is 2rad/sec instead of 1.98
SWITCH TO END PLATES, REMAIN AT -4DEG PITCH																		
270	ZERO						62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
271	ZERO						0.80000	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
272	ZERO						1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
273	ZERO						1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
274	ZERO						1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
275	ZERO						2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
276	ZERO						2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
295	ZERO						3.20081	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
277	ZERO						62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
278	ZERO						0.80000	7.854	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
279	ZERO						1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
280	ZERO						1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
281	ZERO						1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
283	ZERO						2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
284	ZERO						2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
257	ZERO						62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
258	ZERO						1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
259	ZERO						1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
267	ZERO						1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
268	ZERO						2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
269	ZERO						2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
296	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
297	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
298	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
Reg Waves																		
285	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
286	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
287	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
288	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
289	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
290	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
291	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
292	RW	135		2.00	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
293	RW	135		2.00	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
294	RW	135		2.00	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
ADDED REPETITION OF Substructure tests with PLATES AND FOIL1 PHASE = 270																		
299	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	
300	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-45	False	-4	False	
301	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-90	False	-4	False	
302	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-180	False	-4	False	
304	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	0	False	-4	False	
305	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-45	False	-4	False	
306	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-90	False	-4	False	
307	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-180	False	-4	False	
SWITCH TO -8 DEG PITCH																		
314	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
315	ZERO				-		0.80000	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
316	ZERO				-		1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
317	ZERO				-		1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
318	ZERO				-		1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
319	ZERO				-		2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
320	ZERO				-		2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
321	ZERO				-		3.20081	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
325	ZERO				-		62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
326	ZERO				-		1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
327	ZERO				-		1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
328	ZERO				-		1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
329	ZERO				-		2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
330	ZERO				-		2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
308	ZERO				-		62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
309	ZERO				-		1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
310	ZERO				-		1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
311	ZERO				-		1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
312	ZERO				-		2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
313	ZERO				-		2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
322	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
323	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
324	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
Reg Waves																		
331	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
332	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
333	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
334	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
335	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
336	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
337	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
338	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
339	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
340	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
341	RW	133		1.60	0.15	90	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
342	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
343	RW	137		2.404	0.15	90	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
FREE WHEELING TEST																		
344	RW	137		2.404	0.15	Free	Free	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	Started with constant speed and rotor stopped quickly after motor shutdown
ADJUST HEXAPOD YAW ANGLE																		
346	RW	133		1.60	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	
347	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	
349	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	
350	RW	133		1.60	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	30	ZERO		True	-8	False	
351	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	30	ZERO		True	-8	False	
352	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	30	ZERO		True	-8	False	
POLYCHROMATIC WAVE MODE																		
353	PW	151		2.10	0.16	90	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	-8	False	
354	PW	152		2.50	0.16	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	-8	False	
ROTOR FIXED POSITION																		
348	RW	137		2.404	0.15	90		0	fixed	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	

Test num	Wave type	W Calib TestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
SWITCH TO 0 DEG PITCH																		
355	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
356	ZERO				-		0.799998129	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
357	ZERO				-		1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
358	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
359	ZERO				-		2.00	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
360	ZERO				-		2.20	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
361	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
362	ZERO				-		3.200807594	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
377	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
378	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
371	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
372	ZERO				-		1.60	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
373	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
374	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
375	ZERO				-		2.20	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
376	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
Reg Waves																		
379	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
380	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
381	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
382	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
383	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
384	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
385	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
386	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
387	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
388	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ROTOR FIXED POSITION																		
391	RW	136		2.202	0.15	0		0	fixed	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
392	RW	136		2.202	0.15	180		0	fixed	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
389	RW	134		1.803	0.15	90	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
390	RW	136		2.202	0.15	90	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
363	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
364	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
365	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
POLYCHROMATIC WAVE MODE																		
394	PW	151		2.10	0.16	270	1.60	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
395	PW	152		2.50	0.16	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
IRREGULAR WAVE MODE																		
396	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
397	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
398	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
399	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
400	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
401	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
402	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
403	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
404	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
405	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
406	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
408	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
409	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
410	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
411	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
412	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
413	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
414	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
415	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
416	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
417	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
418	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
419	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
420	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
421	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
422	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
423	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
424	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
425	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
426	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
427	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
428	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	

Test num	Wave type	W/CalibTestNum	SpecialWaveDef	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Red_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments	
SWITCH TO -12 DEG PITCH																			
434	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
437	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
438	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
439	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
440	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																			
445	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
446	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
447	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
448	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																			
441	ZERO				-				LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
443	ZERO				-				LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	Undervoltage
444	ZERO				-				LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
Reg Waves																			
456	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
457	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
458	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
459	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
460	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
461	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
462	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
SWITCH TO 4 DEG PITCH																			
489	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
490	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
491	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
492	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
493	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
494	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																			
463	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
464	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
465	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
466	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
467	ZERO				-		2.398	2.620	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
468	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
Reg Waves																		
POSITION CONTROL MODE																		
473	RW	133		1.600	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
474	RW	135		2.000	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
475	RW	138		2.000	0.10	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
482	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
483	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
484	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
485	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
486	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
488	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
SWITCH TO 0 DEG PITCH																		
495	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
496	RW	133		1.600	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
497	RW	135		2.000	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
498	RW	138		2.000	0.10	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
499	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
500	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
501	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	PTO undervoltage
503	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	PTO undervoltage, freewheeling after
506	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	PTO undervoltage, freewheeling after
502	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
504	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
505	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
SWITCH TO 0 DEG PITCH																		
513	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
514	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
515	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
516	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
517	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
518	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
519	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
520	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
524	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
525	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
526	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
527	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
528	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
530	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
573	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
507	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
508	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
509	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
510	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
511	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
512	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
521	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
522	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
523	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
Reg Waves																		
531	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
532	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
533	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
534	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
535	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
536	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
537	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
538	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
539	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
540	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
552	RW	135		2.000	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
568	RW	72		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
569	RW	74		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
570	RW	76		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
SUBSTRUCTURE MOTION TEST																		
558	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	0	True	0	0	
560	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-45	True	0	0	
561	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-90	True	0	0	
562	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-180	True	0	0	
563	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	0	True	0	0	
564	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-45	True	0	0	
565	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-90	True	0	0	
566	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-180	True	0	0	
FOIL COMPLIANCE TESTING																		
571	RW	135		2.000	0.15		2.00	3.141592654	Constant	2	0.6	0	Struct-4	10	True	0	0	short test
572	RW	135		2.000	0.15		2.00	3.141592654	Constant	2	0.6	0	Struct-4	10	True	0	0	problem with rotor position sensor?
567	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.141592654	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075 surge only	10	True	0	0	

Test num	Wave type	W_CalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
FREE WHEELING TEST																		
553	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
554	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
555	RW	137		2.404	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
ROTOR FIXED POSITION																		
549	RW	136		2.202	0.15	0		0	Constant	2	0.6		Zero		True	0	0	
550	RW	136		2.202	0.15	90		0	Constant	2	0.6		Zero		True	0	0	
551	RW	136		2.202	0.15	180		0	Constant	2	0.6		Zero		True	0	0	
556	RW	136		2.202	0.15	0		0	Constant	2	0.755		Zero		True	0	0	
557	RW	136		2.202	0.15	90		0	Constant	2	0.755		Zero		True	0	0	
IRREGULAR WAVE MODE																		
541	IW	154	Seed2	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
542	IW	155	Seed4	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
543	IW	156	Seed5	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
544	IW	158	Seed7	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
545	IW	147	Seed1	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
546	IW	149	Seed3	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
547	IW	150	Seed4	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
548	IW	153	Seed5	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
MOUNT FOIL 2, SWITCH TO -4 DEG PITCH																		
587	ZERO						62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
588	ZERO						1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
589	ZERO						1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
590	ZERO						2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
591	ZERO						2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
592	ZERO						2.398	2.620	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
593	ZERO						3.201	1.963	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
597	ZERO						62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
598	ZERO						1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
599	ZERO						1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
600	ZERO						2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
601	ZERO						2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
602	ZERO						2.398	2.620	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
574	ZERO						62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
575	ZERO						1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
576	ZERO						1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
577	ZERO						2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
578	ZERO						2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
579	ZERO						2.398	2.620	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	

Test num	Wave type	W/CalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
580	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		repeat
584	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		repeat
585	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		repeat
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
594	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	2	0.755	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
595	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	2	0.755	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
596	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	2	0.755	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
Reg Waves																		
603	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
604	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
605	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
606	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
607	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
608	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
609	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
610	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
611	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
612	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
613	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
614	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
615	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
FREE WHEELING TEST																		
616	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
617	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
618	RW	137		2.404	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
619	IW	155	Seed4	2.500	0.16		Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
Substructure drag																		
622	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
623	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
624	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
625	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
626	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
627	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
628	ZERO				-		2.398	2.620	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
629	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
630	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		
631	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		
632	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		
633	ZERO				-		2.398	2.620	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		

B. POLY-CHROMATIC WAVES DEFINITION

Hs-target	Tp-target			
0.16	2.1			
Hs-real	Tp-real	STD over 100*Tp	theta_init	
0.15959596	2.100257	0.039898991	1.13728708	
Spectrum				
T [s]	H [m]	Phase [rad]	f [Hz]	lambda_approx [m]
3.237548	0.044951	2.02444746	0.30887576	15.76100718
2.100257	0.069481	2.70808341	0.47613219	6.88321647
1.565693	0.061975	0.91004525	0.63869501	3.82607695
1.256153	0.037026	2.75556726	0.79608117	2.46278273
1.040710	0.025976	6.08275593	0.96088229	1.6904426
Hs-target	Tp-target			
0.16	2.5			
Hs-real	Tp-real	STD over 100*Tp	theta_init	
0.15957834	2.51794336	0.039894584	1.81341234	
Spectrum				
T [s]	H [m]	Phase [rad]	f [Hz]	lambda_approx [m]
3.81951632	0.04312556	4.79977601	0.26181325	20.6326912
2.51794336	0.06977482	3.38420867	0.39714952	9.86160417
1.8823334	0.06343242	1.26422951	0.53125552	5.52998308
1.48783798	0.03982319	3.78317212	0.67211619	3.45503203
1.24900919	0.0221791	4.91795386	0.80063462	2.43484923

C. WAVE GAUGES CALIBRATION RESULTS

Summary of wave gauge calibration results on the 19th September 2022 before testing and on the 19th October 2022 after the test campaign:

LiftWEC gauge number	ECN gauge number	Gain before testing (mm/V)	Gain after testing
WG 1	WG 21	29.174	No calibration
WG 2	WG 18	28.856	29.961
WG 3	WG 16	28.948	28.487
WG 4	WG 15	28.504	29.45
WG 5	WG 24	29.285	30.027
WG 6	WG 9	29.149	30.498
WG 7	WG 7	29.152	30.261
WG 8	WG 6	28.038	29.056
WG 9	WG 5	28.28	29.536
WG 10	WG 10	28.889	29.667

All calibration certificates are below in this appendix.

29/09/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG21'
 ECN number: 'WG21'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 29.174 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 657.793 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.32 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.21 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.19 (%FS)

Residual Std = 1.000 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 2.00 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/09/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'	Calibration reference standard: 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Serial number: 'WG18'	7 points (2 Sec @800Hz)
ECN number: 'WG18'	3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: 800 'mm'	

Sensitivity = 28.856 ('mm'/Volts)	Residual Std = 0.567 'mm'
Intercept = 661.954 ('mm')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.17 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 1.13 'mm'
Hysteresis = 0.19 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.19 (%FS)	

Calibration by Bruno Pettinotti - 19/09/2022
 Reference documents:
 [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
 [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/10/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG18'
 ECN number: 'WG18'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à huile WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 29.961 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 688.126 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.15 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.13 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.43 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.570 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 1.14 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinatti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/09/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG16'
 ECN number: 'WG16'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 28.948 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 664.870 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.34 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.17 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.07 (%FS)

Residual Std = 1.078 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 2.16 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/10/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG18'
 ECN number: 'WG18'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @800Hz)
 3 étalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 28.487 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 683.112 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.73 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.11 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.22 (%FS)

Residual Std = 2.495 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 4.99 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.001 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/09/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG15'
 ECN number: 'WG15'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @800Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 28.504 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 662.455 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.14 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.18 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.14 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.464 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 0.93 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/10/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'	Calibration reference standard: 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Serial number: 'WG15'	7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
ECN number: 'WG15'	3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: 600 'mm'	

Sensitivity = 29.450 ('mm'/Volts')	Residual Std = 0.804 'mm'
Intercept = 689.379 ('mm')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.11 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 1.61 'mm'
Hysteresis = 0.16 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.51 (%FS)	

Calibration by Bruno Pettinotti - 19/09/2022
Reference documents:
[1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
[2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/09/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG24'
 ECN number: 'WG24'
 Full Range: 800 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 29.285 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 658.118 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.28 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.19 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.12 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.828 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 1.66 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.005 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG24'
 ECN number: 'WG24'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 30.027 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 675.155 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.18 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.16 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.16 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.560 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 1.12 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.005 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 19/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG9'
 ECN number: 'WG9'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 étalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 29.149 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 649.260 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.18 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.13 (%FS)
 Repeatability = 0.14 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.575 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 1.15 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.008 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/10/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG9'
 ECN number: 'WG9'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 30.498 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 677.843 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.42 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.09 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.02 (%FS)

Residual Std = 1.330 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 2.66 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG7'
 ECN number: 'WG7'
 Full Range: 800 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 29.152 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 651.549 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.16 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.09 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.23 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.449 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 0.90 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.003 (%FS)

Calibration by Bruno Pettinotti - 20/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG7'
 ECN number: 'WG7'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 30.261 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 680.704 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.16 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.10 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.02 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.369 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 0.74 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG8'
 ECN number: 'WG8'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 28.038 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 663.121 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.18 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.08 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.23 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.585 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 1.17 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'	Calibration reference standard: 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Serial number: 'WG8'	7 points (2 Sec @800Hz)
ECN number: 'WG8'	3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)
Full Range:800 'mm'	

Sensitivity = 29.056 (mm/Volts)	Residual Std = 0.365 'mm'
Intercept = 692.968 (mm')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.13 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.73 'mm'
Hysteresis = 0.10 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.02 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022
Reference documents:
[1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
[2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'
 Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'
 Serial number: 'WG5'
 ECN number: 'WG5'
 Full Range: 600 'mm'

Calibration reference standard:
 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
 Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
 7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
 3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 28.280 ('mm'/Volts)
 Intercept = 658.141 ('mm')
 Linearity = 0.30 (%FS)
 Hysteresis = 0.13 (%FS)
 Repetability = 0.32 (%FS)

Residual Std = 0.895 'mm'
 Coverage factor = 2
 Expanded uncertainty = 1.79 'mm'
 Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

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STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'	Calibration reference standard: 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Serial number: 'WG5'	7 points (2 Sec @800Hz)
ECN number: 'WG5'	3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)
Full Range:800 'mm'	

Sensitivity = 29.536 ('mm'/Volts')	Residual Std = 0.528 'mm'
Intercept = 888.459 ('mm')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.27 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 1.05 'mm'
Hysteresis = 0.11 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.003 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.06 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022
Reference documents:
[1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
[2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/09/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'	Calibration reference standard: 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Serial number: 'WG10'	7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
ECN number: 'WG10'	3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: 600 'mm'	

Sensitivity = 28.889 ('mm'/Volts')	Residual Std = 0.531 'mm'
Intercept = 654.898 ('mm')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.15 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 1.06 'mm'
Hysteresis = 0.08 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.22 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022
 Reference documents:
 [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
 [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

29/10/2022

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC3D'	Calibration reference standard: 'Banc Etal sonde à houle WDS1000'
Manufacturer: 'Laboratoire'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Serial number: 'WG10'	7 points (2 Sec @600Hz)
ECN number: 'WG10'	3 etalonnage(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: 600 'mm'	

Sensitivity = 29.667 ('mm'/Volts')	Residual Std = 0.381 'mm'
Intercept = 682.977 ('mm')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.18 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.76 'mm'
Hysteresis = 0.10 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.002 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.03 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 20/09/2022
 Reference documents:
 [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
 [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

D. LOAD CELLS CALIBRATION RESULTS

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard: 'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Name: 'F1_pos'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Sensor Reference: 'FOR257'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: '(+/-)490.5' 'N'	

Sensitivity = 247.616 ('N'/mV/Volt)	Residual Std = 0.124 'N'
Intercept = -19.511 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.25 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.004 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.06 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F1_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR257'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range:'(+/-)490.5' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 247.611 ('N'/mV/Volt)	Residual Std = 0.177 'N'
Intercept = 15.075 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.35 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.009 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.09 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard: 'Standard masses M138801 class M1'
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Name: 'F2_pos'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Sensor Reference: 'FOR248'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	

Sensitivity = 148.533 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.386 'N'
Intercept = -9.500 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.77 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.004 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.24 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F2_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR248'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 148.517 ('N'/mV/Volt)	Residual Std = 0.391 'N'
Intercept = 25.015 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.01 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.78 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.004 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.25 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard: 'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Name: 'F3_pos'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Sensor Reference: 'FOR258'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: '(+/-)490.5' 'N'	

Sensitivity = 247.760 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.038 'N'
Intercept = -17.581 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.01 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.08 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.003 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.01 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022
Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F3_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR258'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)490.5' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 247.740 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.165 'N'
Intercept = 17.351 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.02 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.33 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.03 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.004 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.07 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 06/09/2022
Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F4_pos'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR249'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 148.432 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.021 'N'
Intercept = -9.408 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.04 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.003 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.03 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138801 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F4_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR249'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range:'(+/-)294.27' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 148.448 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.021 'N'
Intercept = 24.681 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.01 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.04 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.003 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.01 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard: 'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Name: 'F5_pos'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Sensor Reference: 'FOR259'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: '(+/-)490.5' 'N'	

Sensitivity = 247.135 ('N'/mV/Volt)	Residual Std = 0.030 'N'
Intercept = -15.982 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.06 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.007 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.02 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Sylvain Mazo' - 07/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F5_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR259'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)490.5' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 247.177 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.047 'N'
Intercept = 18.014 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.01 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.09 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.011 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.02 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Sylvain Mazo' - 07/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M13801 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F8_pos'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR248'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 148.445 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.022 'N'
Intercept = -0.005 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.04 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.009 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.02 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 06/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard: 'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Name: 'F6_neg'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Sensor Reference: 'FOR246'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	

Sensitivity = 148.446 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.018 'N'
Intercept = 15.921 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.04 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.010 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.02 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F7_pos'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR260'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)490.5' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 247.501 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.027 'N'
Intercept = -15.917 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.01 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.05 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.006 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.01 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M13801 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F7_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR260'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range:'(+/-)490.5' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 247.439 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.028 'N'
Intercept = 15.970 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.06 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.009 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.01 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022
Reference documents:
(1) ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
(2) ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard: 'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Name: 'F8_pos'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Sensor Reference: 'FOR247'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	

Sensitivity = 134.627 ('N'/mV/Volt)	Residual Std = 0.017 'N'
Intercept = -17.713 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.00 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.03 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.01 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.007 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.01 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

STATIC CALIBRATION REPORT

Project name: 'LIFTWEC'	Calibration reference standard:
Manufacturer: 'HBM'	'Standard masses M138601 class M1'
Sensor Name: 'F8_neg'	Acquisition device: 'Quantum'
Sensor Reference: 'FOR247'	8 points (4 Sec @100Hz)
Full Range: '(+/-)294.27' 'N'	3 Cycle(s) (advance & return)

Sensitivity = 134.638 ('N'/mV/Volt')	Residual Std = 0.017 'N'
Intercept = 0.022 ('N')	Coverage factor = 2
Linearity = 0.01 (%FS)	Expanded uncertainty = 0.03 'N'
Hysteresis = 0.00 (%FS)	Signal Stdev = 0.006 (%FS)
Repeatability = 0.02 (%FS)	

Calibration by 'Bruno Pettinotti' - 05/09/2022

Reference documents:

- [1] ITTC (2002) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.6-02-09 - Calibration of load cells.
- [2] ITTC (2008) Procedures and Guidelines - 7.5-01-03-01 - Uncertainty analysis.

E. TORQUE METER FACTORY CERTIFICATE

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http://www.eth-messtechnik.de
info@eth-messtechnik.de

Werkzertifikat (Factory-Certificate)

Drehmomentsensor Typ DRBK-100
(Torque Transducer Type DRBK-100)

Seriennummer: 809131601
(Serial Number)

Nennmoment:
(Nominal Torque)

<input type="checkbox"/> 0,5Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 5Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 50Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 500Nm
<input type="checkbox"/> 1Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 10Nm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 100Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 1000Nm
<input type="checkbox"/> 2Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 20Nm	<input type="checkbox"/> 200Nm	

Option Drehzahl:
(option speed) Ja

Max. zulässige Abweichung:
(Max. Tolerance of Measurement) $\leq 0,5\%$

Ergebnis der Drehmomentprüfung:
(Result of torque test) **uneingeschränkt einsetzbar**
(for use without restriction)

Ergebnis der Sichtprüfung:
(Result of visual inspection) **ok**

Der Aufnehmer erfüllt die im Datenblatt angegebenen Spezifikationen.
(The Transducer meets the specifications mentioned in the data-sheet)

Datum: 04.09.2019
(Date)

Prüfer: Andreas Frost
(Examiner)

Unterschrift:
(Signature)

Wir empfehlen eine Re-Kalibrierung 24 Monate nach Kalibrierdatum diese Produktes.
(24 months after date of calibration a re-calibration of this sensor is recommended)

Alle zur Kalibrierung verwendeten Geräte sind rückführbar auf nationale Normale, Normalmesseinrichtungen- und verfahren zur Darstellung der physikalischen Einheiten in Übereinstimmung mit dem internationalen Einheitensystem (SI)
(All Devices used for calibration can be tracked back to national standards, physical units comply with the international system of units, SI)

F. CENTRIFUGAL FORCE MEASUREMENT RESULTS WITHOUT WINGLETS

	Pitch1 (deg)	-4		Pitch2 (deg)	4		No winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
73	1.96	5.48	0.29	5.52	0.00	5.86	0.49	5.50	0.56
74	3.93	5.49	0.46	5.55	0.42	5.70	0.55	5.47	0.46
75	7.85	5.48	0.50	5.52	0.52	5.70	0.56	5.49	0.51
76	12	5.44	0.56	5.51	0.56	5.76	0.57	5.54	0.52
	Pitch1 (deg)	-8		Pitch2 (deg)	0		No winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
78	1.96	5.44	0.30	5.69	0.24	5.70	0.48	5.44	0.58
79	3.93	5.47	0.48	5.64	0.41	5.65	0.54	5.42	0.60
80	7.85	5.43	0.58	5.62	0.44	5.67	0.53	5.41	0.65
81	12	5.43	0.56	5.58	0.50	5.75	0.58	5.48	0.61
	Pitch1 (deg)	4		Pitch2 (deg)	0		No winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
83	1.96	5.33	0.08	5.79	0.29	5.67	0.48	5.44	0.57
84	3.93	5.37	0.38	5.73	0.45	5.54	0.54	5.43	0.55
85	7.85	5.33	0.47	5.67	0.53	5.53	0.57	5.41	0.56
86	12	5.32	0.53	5.60	0.57	5.60	0.57	5.47	0.54
	Pitch1 (deg)	-12		Pitch2 (deg)	0		No winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
88	1.96	5.54	0.13	5.84	0.08	5.76	0.45	5.43	0.57
89	3.93	5.57	0.40	5.77	0.40	5.71	0.54	5.44	0.56
90	7.85	5.55	0.52	5.69	0.53	5.69	0.58	5.42	0.56
91	12	5.51	0.60	5.61	0.57	5.78	0.59	5.47	0.54
	Pitch1 (deg)	0		Pitch2 (deg)	0		No winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
93	1.96	5.41	0.17	5.86	0.21	5.60	0.45	5.42	0.57
94	3.93	5.41	0.39	5.75	0.45	5.53	0.53	5.40	0.56
95	7.85	5.40	0.48	5.70	0.52	5.55	0.56	5.41	0.56
96	12	5.36	0.54	5.62	0.57	5.64	0.57	5.46	0.54

G. CENTRIFUGAL FORCE MEASUREMENT RESULTS WITH WINGLETS

	Pitch1 (deg)	0		Pitch2 (deg)	0		Winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
98	1.96	5.75	0.45	6.01	0.07	5.93	0.54	5.85	0.61
99	3.93	5.77	0.48	6.01	0.41	5.92	0.59	5.84	0.59
100	7.85	5.77	0.43	5.98	0.46	5.94	0.67	5.85	0.64
101	12	5.76	0.49	5.98	0.48	6.07	0.68	5.87	0.65
	Pitch1 (deg)	-4		Pitch2 (deg)	4		Winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
103	1.96	5.85	0.44	6.01	-0.22	6.07	0.49	5.82	0.58
104	3.93	5.86	0.52	6.03	0.34	6.02	0.54	5.79	0.58
105	7.85	5.84	0.57	5.97	0.50	6.01	0.58	5.75	0.58
106	12	5.80	0.62	5.93	0.53	6.12	0.61	5.79	0.59
	Pitch1 (deg)	-8		Pitch2 (deg)	0		Winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
108	1.96	5.90	0.35	6.07	-0.33	6.08	0.47	5.88	0.59
109	3.93	5.44	1.18	6.23	-0.12	6.25	0.20	5.67	0.95
110	7.85	5.77	0.75	6.04	0.39	6.12	0.49	5.79	0.68
111	12	5.80	0.71	5.98	0.49	6.20	0.57	5.84	0.63
	Pitch1 (deg)	4		Pitch2 (deg)	0		Winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
113	1.96	5.76	0.34	6.15	-0.15	5.92	0.44	5.87	0.58
114	3.93	5.78	0.48	6.12	0.33	5.92	0.54	5.84	0.57
115	7.85	5.75	0.55	6.05	0.51	5.92	0.59	5.81	0.57
116	12	5.71	0.60	5.99	0.55	6.02	0.61	5.84	0.57
	Pitch1 (deg)	-12		Pitch2 (deg)	0		Winglets		
Test number	Rad/sec	Mass_F1	Mass_F2	Mass_F3	Mass_F4	Mass_F5	Mass_F6	Mass_F7	Mass_F8
118	1.96	5.96	0.28	6.18	-0.09	6.13	0.46	5.84	0.57
119	3.93	5.98	0.49	6.13	0.36	6.13	0.54	5.83	0.57
120	7.85	5.95	0.58	6.07	0.51	6.14	0.59	5.81	0.58
121	12	5.91	0.65	6.01	0.56	6.24	0.62	5.84	0.58